

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Proceedings Book of The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature and Culture Research

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ÖN SÖZ

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 04–08 Kasım 2025 tarihleri arasında Türkiye'nin Antalya kentinde gerçekleştirilmiş; dil, edebiyat ve kültür alanlarını disiplinlerarası bir bakış açısıyla ele alan önemli bir bilimsel buluşma platformu olmuştur. Kongre, Saybiller Topluluğu organizasyonunda; başta Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi (Türkiye) ve Carthage University (Tunus) olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının akademik desteğiyle düzenlenmiştir.

Kongre kapsamında, farklı akademik gelenekleri ve araştırma perspektiflerini temsil eden 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı bilim insanlarıyla buluşturulmuştur. Ayrıca Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça dillerinde yapılan çağrılarla geniş bir uluslararası katılım sağlanmıştır. Bu çok dilli ve kapsayıcı çağrı süreci sonucunda gönderilen bildirimler, bilimsel etik ve kalite ilkeleri doğrultusunda hakem değerlendirme sürecinden geçirilmiştir. Yapılan değerlendirmeler neticesinde Türkiye'den 34, Türkiye dışından ise Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Katar, Kuveyt, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı ve Ürdün olmak üzere 13 farklı ülkeden 114 bildiri, kongre programında yer almış; böylece toplam 148 bildiri bilim dünyasıyla paylaşılmıştır.

Bu kongre kitabında yer alan çalışmalar; dil, edebiyat ve kültür araştırmalarında güncel kuramsal yaklaşımları, özgün analizleri ve farklı coğrafyalardan gelen akademik deneyimleri bir araya getirmektedir. Kongre süreci, özellikle uluslararası ve kültürlerarası iş birliğine dayalı araştırmaların bilimsel bilginin evrenselleşmesi ve akademik etkileşimin sürdürülebilirliği açısından taşıdığı önemi bir kez daha ortaya koymuştur.

Bu bağlamda araştırmacıların; disiplinlerarası çalışmalara daha fazla yönelmeleri, ortak projeler ve çok yazarlı uluslararası yayınlar aracılığıyla akademik etkileşimi güçlendirmeleri ve farklı dillerde bilimsel üretim yaparak çalışmalarının görünürlüğünü artırmaları önem arz etmektedir. Üniversitelerin, araştırma merkezlerinin ve diğer paydaşların ise genç araştırmacıları destekleyen, uluslararası akademik ağları teşvik eden ve nitelikli bilimsel üretimi sürdürülebilir kılan yapılar oluşturmaya devam etmeleri gerekmektedir.

Bu kongrenin ve elinizdeki kitabın; alan yazınına anlamlı katkılar sunmasını, yeni akademik iş birliklerine zemin hazırlamasını ve dil, edebiyat ile kültür araştırmalarında nitelikli bilimsel üretimi teşvik etmesini temenni eder; kongrenin gerçekleştirilmesinde emeği geçen tüm kurumlara, hakemlere, davetli konuşmacılara ve değerli araştırmacılara teşekkür ederiz.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

PREFACE

The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature, and Culture Research, held in Antalya, Türkiye, between November 4–8, 2025, constituted a significant academic platform that brought together studies in language, literature, and culture within an interdisciplinary framework. The congress was organized by the Saybilder Community, with the academic support of several higher education institutions, most notably Mardin Artuklu University and Carthage University.

Within the scope of the congress, invited speakers from six different countries met with scholars representing diverse academic traditions and research perspectives. In addition, calls for papers were announced in Turkish, English, and Arabic, enabling broad international participation. Following these multilingual calls, the submitted papers underwent a peer-review process conducted in accordance with scientific and ethical standards. As a result of the evaluations, a total of 148 papers were included in the scientific program, comprising 34 papers from Türkiye and 114 papers from 13 different countries, namely the United Arab Emirates, Algeria, Indonesia, Morocco, Palestine, Iraq, Iran, Qatar, Kuwait, Egypt, Syria, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and Jordan.

The studies presented in this proceedings book brought together contemporary theoretical approaches, original analyses, and diverse academic experiences from different geographical regions in the fields of language, literature, and culture. In particular, the congress clearly demonstrated the importance of international and intercultural collaborative research, emphasizing its crucial role in the universal dissemination of scientific knowledge and the establishment of sustainable interaction among different academic traditions.

In this context, researchers are encouraged to further engage in interdisciplinary studies, to strengthen academic interaction through joint projects and international co-authored publications, and to enhance the visibility of their research by producing scholarly work in multiple languages. Universities, research centers, and other stakeholders are likewise encouraged to continue supporting early-career researchers, fostering international academic networks, and developing sustainable structures for high-quality scientific production.

It is our sincere hope that this congress and the present proceedings book will contribute meaningfully to the existing literature, inspire new academic collaborations, and promote rigorous scientific research in the fields of language, literature, and cultural studies. We would like to express our gratitude to all institutions, reviewers, invited speakers, and distinguished researchers who contributed to the successful realization of this congress.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University
Chair of the Organizing Committee

المقدمة

انعقد المؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغة والأدب والدراسات الثقافية في مدينة أنطاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، وشكّل منصة علمية متميزة جمعت دراسات اللغة والأدب والثقافة في إطارٍ متعدد التخصصات. وقد نُظّم المؤتمر من قِبَل مجتمع سايبيلدر (Saybilder)، بدعمٍ علمي من عدد من مؤسسات التعليم العالي، وفي مقدمتها جامعة ماردين أرتقلو وجامعة قرطاج (Carthage University).

وشهد المؤتمر مشاركة متحدثين مدعويين من ست دول مختلفة، حيث التقى هؤلاء بنخبة من الباحثين الذين يمثلون مدارس أكاديمية ورؤى بحثية متنوعة. كما أُطلقت دعوات المشاركة باللغات التركية والإنجليزية والعربية، ما أسهم في تحقيق مشاركة دولية واسعة. وبعد ذلك، خضعت البحوث المقدّمة لعملية تحكيم علمي وفق المعايير الأكاديمية والأخلاقية المعتمدة. وأسفرت هذه العملية عن إدراج 148 بحثاً ضمن البرنامج العلمي، منها 34 بحثاً من تركيا و 114 بحثاً من 13 دولة هي: الإمارات العربية المتحدة، الجزائر، إندونيسيا، المغرب، فلسطين، العراق، إيران، قطر، الكويت، مصر، سوريا، المملكة العربية السعودية، والأردن.

وقد جمعت الدراسات الواردة في هذا الكتاب بين أحدث المقاربات النظرية، والتحليلات الأصيلة، والتجارب الأكاديمية المتنوعة من مختلف المناطق الجغرافية في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة. كما أبرز المؤتمر بوضوح أهمية البحوث القائمة على التعاون الدولي والتفاعل الثقافي، لما لها من دور محوري في تعميم المعرفة العلمية وبناء تفاعل أكاديمي مستدام بين التقاليد العلمية المختلفة.

وانطلاقاً من نتائج هذا اللقاء العلمي، يُشجّع الباحثون على توسيع نطاق الدراسات البيئية، وتعزيز المشاريع المشتركة، والإسهام في النشر العلمي الدولي المشترك، إضافة إلى الإنتاج البحثي متعدد اللغات بما يزيد من انتشار الأبحاث وتأثيرها. كما تُدعى الجامعات ومراكز البحث وسائر الشركاء الأكاديميين إلى مواصلة دعم الباحثين الشباب، وتعزيز الشبكات العلمية الدولية، وبناء هياكل مستدامة تضمن جودة واستمرارية الإنتاج العلمي.

وإذ نأمل أن يكون هذا المؤتمر وهذا الكتاب قد أسهما في إثراء الأدبيات العلمية وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي، فإننا نتقدم بخالص الشكر والتقدير إلى جميع المؤسسات المشاركة، والمحكمين، والمتحدثين المدعويين، والباحثين الكرام الذين أسهموا في إنجاح هذا الحدث العلمي.

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The Uses of Translation Techniques to Achieve an Appropriate Translation

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Abstract

The title of this research is The Uses of Translation Techniques to Achieve Appropriate Translation. Translation in general is replacing a text in one language to another text in another language. One can say that translation is a means of communication. Translation techniques have received a great deal of attention by western theorists of translation. However, no work concerning the study of “the uses of translation technique was carried out. This present study is an attempt to bridge that gap. It is known that modern language teaching overuses and misuses translation techniques in the classroom due to failure in order to understand the principles of teaching. Therefore, the current paper tackles the uses of translation technique to get an appropriate translation. This paper aims to help students of translation department as well as translators to develop and reinforce their competence besides their knowledge regarding English language. Hence, translation is considered as a pedagogical device. Added to these, translation lets learners and readers communicate into and from the foreign language. To doing this job, learners will recognize the differences and similarities in lexicons, syntactic structures, semantic elements, cultural norms, style and pragmatic elements of both languages, namely English and Arabic. The main findings of this study are that translation can be regarded as a very good device for using many techniques in order to get an appropriate translation. These techniques are borrowing which is the involving the uses of some expressions in original text, calque which means to translate the phrase word by word, transposition which means the moving of grammatical category without any changes , literal translation which is applied and closed in both language and cultural norms and adaptation which means to replace the original text with one that is better suited to the culture of the target language .

Keywords: Techniques, translation, strategy, appropriate

Introduction

First, this research, which its title is the uses of translation techniques to achieve an appropriate translation are an attempt to show some techniques to get successful translation. I would like to say that translation will be presented as a process, which begins with the source text, analyzes this text into semantic structure and pragmatic elements then rebuild them to get an appropriate translation. This is a general way of looking at the translation process. Translation in general is more complicated than such an overview might indicate. In some cases, the translator will analyze the source text to find the accurate meaning, then restructuring this meaning in the receptor language and moving back to see the analysis, which he has done. At times, even while he is working on the final draft, the translator will go back and re-read things he looked at his preparation.

Aims of the Study

This paper aims at:

1. Showing and resolving the problems, which may face translators when they translating any text or sentences from English into Arabic.
2. Showing some cases that the translator should use many techniques to get an appropriate translation.
3. Taking into consideration that the concept of 'adequacy' is more useful than the concept of 'equivalence', in translation especially when there is a difference between cultures.

Hypotheses

This study hypothesized that:

1. There is no one to one formal correspondence between the source language and target language in many contexts.
2. Transferring the structures of the source language to target language is necessary in order to be able to arrive an appropriate rendering.

1. Translation Techniques vs. Translation Methods

One can say that there is a difference between a translation method and translation technique. It can be said that the translation method is applied to the entire text whereas a translation technique may vary within the same text and it depends on the specific verbal elements to be translated. It has many categories namely, borrowing, calque, literal translation, and transposition.

1.1. Borrowing

It is a translation technique, which involves the using of the same expression in original text of the target text. The word is always written in italics. This is about reproducing an expression in the original text as it is. In this sense, it is a translation technique that does not actually translate. (Vinay and Darblent, 1995).

e.g : *cafe* is a French word entered to English language.

1.2. Calque

The translator will create such neologism in the target language by adopting the structure of the source language when he or she uses a calque. It means to translate the phrase word by word. (Vinay and Darblent, 1995).

e.g (television) in English language whereas *Fernesehen* in German Language.

1.3. Literal Translation

Literal translation is also called metaphase which means a word -for- word translation, achieving a text in the target language which is as correct as it is idiomatic. Vinay states that literal translation can only be applied with languages, which are extremely close in cultural terms. It is acceptable only if the translated sentences retain with the same syntax, style and meaning as the original text. (Catford, 1965).

e.g (residual heat) in Russian is translated into after heat in English.

1.4. Transposition

Transposition means that the translator is moving from one grammatical category to another without altering the meaning of the text. This translation technique introduces a change in grammatical structure. (Venuti,1995).

e.g (poetry) is changed into song.

2. Adaptation

It is also called cultural substitution or cultural equivalent, which means a cultural element that, replaces the original text with one that is better suited to the culture of the target language. This achieves a more comprehensive text.

e.g. baseball football.

Many authors like Michel Ballard and Michel have established other methods of translation, such as explication which means introducing specific details in the text of the target language and compensation (Bernardini 2016).

3. Translation Techniques and Procedures

Translation techniques and procedures are depending on a variety of contextual factors. They are used for sentences and any units of language rather than whole texts. In what follows the fundamental techniques and procedures relevant to the actual performing of the task will be explained in some details.

3.1. Nida's Translation Procedures

Nida (1995) states that fundamental procedures which are relevant to the actual performing of the task of translation can be divided roughly into two categories: 1. Technical Procedures: It is concerning the process which followed by the translator in converting source language text into receptor language text.

2. Organizational Procedures. It is involving the general organization in terms of a single translator or many. (Nida, 1995: 224).

3.2 Technical Procedures

It consists three phases namely, (a) analysis of the respective both languages, (b) careful study of the source language text and (c) determining the appropriate equivalents. (Nida, 1995: 225).

3.3 Organizational Procedures

Technical procedures apply to all types of translating, but in some cases will face different types of procedural problems. Added to this, revisions are in some ways a good deal more difficult than original translations, and hence often involve very complex procedures, usually because of stakes. (Nida, 1995: 225).

3.4. Newmark's Translating Procedures

Newmark focuses on the translation procedures which was proposed by him in (1988 and 1991). These procedures are as follows: **(a) Transference:** It is the process of transferring (SL) word to (TL) word as a translation procedure. It is the same as Catford's transference, which relates to the conversion of different alphabets. So, the word then becomes a "loan word". Some authorities deny that this is a translation procedure, but no other term is appropriate if a translator decides to use an SL word for his text. However, when the translator has to decide whether to transfer a word unfamiliar in the target language, which in principle should be a SL cultural word whose referent is peculiar to the SL culture, then he usually complements it with a second translation procedure. Generally, only cultural "objects" should be transferred; the vogue for transferring so-called "national characteristics" should be abandoned. It is not the translator's job to assist any SL advertiser's financial but at the same time, one cannot be rigid. The media or the experts, will transfer words whether the translators like it or not. (Newmark :1991).

(b) Naturalization: This procedure succeeds to adapt the SL word to the normal pronunciation, then to the normal morphology of the TL.

(c) Cultural Equivalent: It means to translate SL cultural word by a TL cultural word; thus baccalaureate is translated as (the French) "A" level, or Abitur (Matura) as (the German) "A" level; Palais Bourbon as (the French). The above examples are cultural equivalents. Their translation uses are limited, since they are not accurate, but they can be used in general texts and to show a brief explanation to readers who are ignorant of the relevant SL culture. (Newmark , 1981and 1988).

(d)Functional Equivalent: This procedure applied to cultural words, which requires the uses of culture-free word; it therefore neutralizes the SL wordand sometimes adds a particular thus, baccalaureate "French secondary school leaving exam". This procedure, which is a cultural componential analysis, is the most accurate way of translating.(AL- Sulaimaan , 2016:209).

3.5. Vinay and Darbelent's Translation Techniques

Vinay and Darbelent (1995) used two types of techniques. They are as follows:

(1) Equivalence : Vinay and Darbelnet's (1995) are referring to notices, familiar alternatives, phrases and idioms-in other words, different ways of rendering the clichés and standard aspects of language.

(2) Adaptation: It means to use a recognized equivalent between two situations. This is a matter of cultural equivalence, e.g. "dear sir" translated to .(سيدي العزيز)

3.6 Graedler's Techniques

Graedler (2000) puts some techniques for translating culture, which are:

(1)Make a new word.

(2)Explaining the meaning of the SL expressions.

(3)Preserving the SL term intact.

(4)Opting for a word in the TL, which seems similar to or has the same "relevance" as the SL term.

3.7. Harvey's Translation Techniques

Defining culture-bound terms as the terms which "refer to concepts, institutions and personnel which are specific to the SL culture" (Harvey,2000): He puts forward the following four major techniques for translating culture-bound terms.

(1)Functional Equivalence: It means to use a referent in the target language culture whose function is similar to that of the source language referent. As Harvey (2000) writes, authors are divided over the merits of this technique. Weststein (1991) describes it as "the ideal method of translation" while Sarcevic (1985) asserts that it is "misleading and should be avoided".

(2)Formal Equivalence: It means word-for-word translation.

(3)Transcription

It stands at the far end of SL-oriented strategies. If the term is formally transparent in the context, it may be used alone. In other cases. Particularly where no knowledge of the SL by the reader is presumed, transcription is accompanied by an explanation or a translator's note.

(4) Descriptive: or self-explanatory translationIt uses generic terms to convey the meaning. It is appropriate in a wide variety of contexts where formal equivalence is considered insufficiently clear. In a text aimed at a specialized reader, it can be helpful to add the original SL term to avoid ambiguity.

4. Translation Strategies: The translation's strategies are involving the main tasks of choosing the foreign text to be translated. These tasks are determined by different factors namely cultural, economic, and political. A translation project may conform to values currently dominating the target-language culture, taking a conservative and openly assimilations approach to the foreign text. Alliteratively, a translation project may resist and aiming to revise the dominant by drawing on the

marginal, restoring foreign texts recovering residual values such as archaic texts and translation methods, as well as cultivating emergent ones.

Strategies in producing translations inevitably emerge in response to domestic cultural situations. However, some are deliberately domesticating in their handling of the foreign text, while others can be described as foreignizing, motivated to preserve linguistic and cultural differences by deviating from prevailing domestic values. Krings (1986) defines translation strategy as "translator's potentially conscious plans for solving concrete translation problems in the framework of a concrete translation task" and Seguinot (1986) believes that there are at least three global strategies employed by the translators namely, (a) translating without interruption for as long as possible (b) correcting surface errors immediately (c) leaving the monitoring for qualitative or stylistic errors in the text to the revision stage. Moreover, Loescher (1991) defines translation strategy as "a potentially conscious procedure for solving a problem faced in translating a text. He stated in this definition, the notion of consciousness is significant in distinguishing strategies, which are used by the learners or translators. Furthermore, Bell (1998) differentiates between global and local strategies and confirms that this distinction results from various kinds of translation problems. According to Venuti (1991) indicates that translation strategies "involve the basic tasks of choosing the foreign text to be translated and developing a method to translate it". He employs the concepts of domesticating and foreignizing to refer to translation strategies.

5. Our Translation's Techniques and Strategies of

Although some stylists consider translation, "sprinkled with footnotes" undesirable their uses can assist the TT readers to make better judgment of the ST contents. In general, it seems that the procedures "functional equivalent would have a higher potential for conveying the concepts underlying the texts embedded in a text. Added to these, it can be claimed that a combination of these strategies would result in a more accurate understanding of the texts than other procedures. Different strategies adopted by translators in rendering allusions seem to play a crucial role in recognition. If a novice translator renders a literary text without paying adequate attention to the allusions, the connotations are likely not to be transferred because of the translator's failure to acknowledge them. It seems necessary for an acceptable translation to produce the same effects on the TT readers as those created by the original work on its readers. It can be claimed that the best translation method seem to be the one which allows translator to utilize "notes". Furthermore, employing "notes" in the translation, as both a translation strategy and a translation technique. All that have been mentioned cannot be achieved unless the translator is aware of both languages and both cultures. Hence, a contrastive study of both languages is needed and favorable. Consequently, grammar translation should be used in teaching English in departments of English, since a would-be translator must be bilingual and bi-cultural.

6. Grammar Translation Method

The Grammar-Translation Method focuses on the teaching of the foreign language grammar through the presentation of rules together with some exceptions and lists of vocabulary translated into the mother tongue. Translation is considered the most important classroom technique. The main procedure of an ordinary lesson follows this plan: a presentation of a grammatical rule followed by a list of vocabulary and translation exercises from selected texts. Other strategies and procedures can be the following:

- (a) Answering comprehension questions on the text.
- (b) Students find antonyms and synonyms words in the text.
- (c) Vocabulary is selected from the reading texts and memorized.
- (d) Sentences are formed using new words.

7.Strategies of Grammar Translation Method at Class.

1. It is professor biased.2. The vocabularies which taught through wordlists and translation should be memorized. 3. Practice should be based on translation of texts from SL text to TL text.4. It elaborates presentation of grammar rules. 5. It depends on memorization of grammar rules and vocabulary. 6. Vocabulary exercises include antonyms and synonyms, and definitions.7. Composition exercises based on topics from reading texts. 8. Reading passages even at low levels, with comprehension questions.

Conclusion

There are many reasons for the purposeful inclusion of translation techniques in translation.1. It refers to the communicative interaction between teacher and students and among the students themselves.2. It will be a conscious process of language learning, which is engages the learners in the learning process.3. Translation techniques help students to develop their reading comprehension as well as spoken abilities.4. They will be as evaluative techniques for checking students reading comprehension of a particular text. 5. The students in the class should be initially given prior guidance on the practical procedures of translation activity and encouraged to work in groups to get the best translation.6. The students should be familiarized with semantic elements, like synonymy, hyponymy, antonym, collocation expressions, and idiomatic expressions. 7. The students must be familiarized with pragmatic elements such as intentionality, speech acts, ambiguity whether pragmatic ambiguity or any other type of ambiguity. 8. Familiarizing the students of translation with cultural norms is very important.9. Teaching tradition is not a matter of replacing words with words or structures with structures. It is a matter of analysis of the whole elements of the source language and synthesis of all elements of target language.

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يمثل هذا الكتاب الإصدار العلمي الرسمي للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر لبحوث اللغة والأدب والثقافة، الذي عُقد في أطلاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، بتنظيم من جمعية سايبيلدر وبالشراكة مع عدد من الجامعات والمؤسسات الأكاديمية في تركيا وتونس ودول أخرى. ويضم هذا العمل مجموعة منتقاة من الأبحاث المحكمة التي اجتازت مراحل المراجعة العلمية وفق معايير الجودة والأمانة الأكاديمية.

تعكس الدراسات الواردة في هذا المجلد التنوع المعرفي والغنى المنهجي في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة، كما تبرز قيمة التعاون العلمي الدولي من خلال مشاركة باحثين من ثلاث عشرة دولة. ويؤكد هذا الإصدار أهمية دعم الحراك البحثي متعدد التخصصات وتشجيع الإنتاج العلمي بلغات مختلفة بما يعزز حضور المعرفة في فضاء البحث العالمي.

وإذ نقدّم هذا الكتاب إلى المجتمع الأكاديمي، نعبّر عن تقديرنا للجهات الداعمة والهيئات العلمية والمحكمين والباحثين المشاركين، آمليّن أن يسهم هذا العمل في تعزيز الدراسات ذات الصلة وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي المستدام.

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